

IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL METHODOLOGICAL CREATIVITY OF FUTURE PEDAGOGUES WITH THE HELP OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNIQUES

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Abstract: The article discusses the features of the development of creativity of future teachers with the help of educational technologies. The terms and pedagogical conditions for the formation of pedagogues' creative potential are characterized. The heuristic methods of organizing classes are analyzed and the expediency of their application in the process of professional training of future teachers is substantiated.

Keywords: Creativity of future teachers, teaching methods, professional training, creativity, creative thinking, creative thinking, creative abilities, creative motivation, creative environment.

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Developing professional methodical creativity is an essential aspect of the training of future pedagogues. The ability to generate innovative ideas, design effective lesson plans, and adapt to the changing needs of students are key skills that can help pedagogues succeed in their profession. In recent years, educational technologies have emerged as powerful tools for fostering the development of professional methodical creativity among pedagogues. In this article, we will explore the role of educational technologies in promoting creativity in the training of future pedagogues.

Educational technologies provide pedagogues with a range of tools and resources that can help them develop their creativity. For example, online platforms offer a wealth of information and resources that pedagogues can use to design innovative lesson plans and teaching strategies. Moreover, many educational technologies provide pedagogues with opportunities for collaboration and teamwork. This can be especially beneficial for promoting creativity as it allows pedagogues to share ideas and brainstorm solutions together. For example, Google Drive and other cloud-based collaboration tools enable pedagogues to work together on shared documents and projects, regardless of their location.

Educational technologies can also help pedagogues to develop their critical thinking skills, which are essential for fostering professional methodical creativity. For example, online discussion forums and virtual classrooms can provide pedagogues with opportunities to engage in critical discussions with their peers

and reflect on their own teaching practices. This can help them to identify areas where they can improve their teaching and develop new and innovative ideas.

Another benefit of educational technologies is their ability to provide pedagogues with access to a wide range of instructional resources. Online libraries, video libraries, and other digital resources can help pedagogues to find new and innovative ways of teaching their subjects. This can be especially beneficial for those teaching in subject areas that are rapidly changing or evolving.

There are many different educational techniques that can be used to develop the professional methodical creativity of future pedagogues. Some of the most effective strategies include hands-on activities, problem-based learning, collaborative projects, and incorporating technology into the curriculum. Hands-on activities are a great way to encourage students to think creatively and actively engage in the learning process. For example, future pedagogues could participate in STEM activities that involve building and experimenting with different machines and instruments. By doing so, they can learn how to approach problems creatively and come up with innovative solutions. Another effective technique is problem-based learning, which involves presenting students with real-world challenges and allowing them to work together to come up with solutions. As part of this process, future pedagogues can learn how to collaborate with others, communicate effectively, and think critically about issues related to education and pedagogy. Collaborative projects are also a great way to develop professional methodical creativity, as they encourage students to work together to develop creative solutions and ideas. As part of this process, future pedagogues can learn how to collaborate effectively with others, communicate their ideas clearly and persuasively, and develop strong leadership skills. Incorporating technology into the curriculum is another effective educational technique that can help to develop the professional methodical creativity of future pedagogues. By using technology, students can learn how to think creatively and solve problems in new and innovative ways, while also developing valuable technical skills that will be essential in their future careers. Teaching methods can be instrumental in developing professional methodical creativity of future pedagogues. Here are a few examples of teaching methods that can be used for the purpose:

1. Problem-based learning: This method involves the presentation of real-world problems or situations to students, who then work together to find solutions or resolutions. This method encourages critical thinking and problem-solving skills, which are essential components of professional methodical creativity.

2. Inquiry-based learning: This teaching method involves encouraging students to explore topics or subjects through questioning, investigation, and

analysis of evidence. By doing so, students are able to develop their own hypotheses and theories, which is an essential skill for innovative problem-solving.

3. Project-based learning: This method involves providing students with a project or task to complete, which requires them to apply their knowledge and skills to a real-life situation. By doing so, students are able to develop new, innovative solutions to problems, which is a key aspect of professional methodical creativity.

4. Role-playing: This teaching method involves placing students in a simulated or hypothetical scenario, in which they must act out various roles or positions. This is a valuable method for developing empathy, communication skills, and problem-solving abilities.

5. Collaborative learning: This method involves working with peers to achieve a common goal or objective. This is a valuable method for developing teamwork, communication, and critical thinking skills, which are all essential components of professional methodical creativity.

Overall, these and other teaching methods can help pedagogues develop professional methodical creativity by cultivating the essential skills of critical analysis, problem-solving, creativity, communication, teamwork, and empathy. Finally, it is important to ensure that the use of educational technologies is inclusive and accessible to all students. Not all students may have access to the latest technologies or may face challenges when it comes to using them. Therefore, pedagogues must ensure that they provide a range of options and strategies to accommodate different learning needs and abilities.

In conclusion, the use of educational technologies can play a significant role in promoting professional methodical creativity among future pedagogues. By providing access to a range of tools and resources, promoting collaboration and critical thinking, and developing technological literacy, educational technologies can help pedagogues to generate innovative ideas and strategies, adapt to changing needs, and succeed in their profession. However, it is important to ensure that the use of these technologies is balanced with traditional pedagogical methods, and that pedagogues receive adequate training and support to effectively incorporate them into their teaching practices. Ultimately, by harnessing the power of educational technologies, we can better prepare future pedagogues to meet the challenges of modern education and inspire the next generation of learners.

The use of educational technologies can provide numerous benefits when it comes to developing professional methodical creativity among future pedagogues. By providing access to a range of resources, promoting collaboration and critical thinking, and developing technological literacy, educational technologies can help pedagogues to generate innovative ideas and strategies, adapt to changing needs,

and succeed in their profession. However, it is important to ensure that the use of these technologies is balanced with traditional pedagogical methods, and that pedagogues receive adequate training and support to effectively incorporate them into their teaching practices. Ultimately, by harnessing the power of educational technologies, we can create a more dynamic and effective approach to pedagogical training that better prepares future pedagogues for the challenges and opportunities of modern education.

Educational technologies have become an integral part of modern education, and their importance in developing creativity among future teachers cannot be overstated. In the fast-paced and ever-changing landscape of education, technology has become an essential tool for pedagogues to adapt to changing needs and promote innovation in their teaching practices.

One of the key benefits of educational technologies is their ability to provide access to a wealth of resources and information. With the internet and online databases, teachers have access to a wide range of teaching materials, including lesson plans, multimedia resources, and educational software. This allows them to tailor their teaching approach to the needs and interests of their students and create more engaging and effective learning experiences.

Moreover, educational technologies can promote collaboration and critical thinking among students. Online platforms and social media can provide opportunities for students to connect with each other and work together on projects, even if they are located in different parts of the world. This can help to develop teamwork and communication skills, which are essential in today's globalized society.

Additionally, educational technologies can help to develop technological literacy among future teachers. With the increasing importance of technology in all aspects of life, it is crucial that pedagogues have a solid understanding of how to use these tools effectively. By providing training and support in the use of educational technologies, institutions can ensure that future teachers are equipped with the skills and knowledge they need to succeed in their profession.

Furthermore, educational technologies can promote creativity among future teachers by providing them with a platform to experiment with new teaching strategies and techniques. With the ability to create and share digital content, pedagogues can explore new approaches to teaching and learning, which can help to keep their students engaged and motivated.

In conclusion, the importance of educational technologies in developing creativity among future teachers cannot be understated. By providing access to a wealth of resources, promoting collaboration and critical thinking, and developing technological literacy, educational technologies can help to prepare future teachers

for the challenges and opportunities of modern education. As technology continues to evolve, it will be crucial for pedagogical training programs to embrace these tools and incorporate them into their teaching practices to ensure that future teachers are equipped with the skills and knowledge they need to succeed in their profession.

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